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Deployment of Instructional Materials and Spatial Distribution of Teachers for Teaching Upper Basic Social Studies in Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The paper examined deployment of instructional materials and spatial distribution of teachers for teaching Upper Basic Social Studies in Delta State, Nigeria. The paper x-rayed how instructional materials being used by teachers enhance the teaching and learning of Social Studies. The paper made use of secondary data in the evaluation of variables of instructional material and spatial distribution of social studies teachers at the Upper Basic level of the state. A conceptual model by Live Tiles was adopted for the study. The emphasis of this model to this investigation is that it lays more light on the benefit inherent in teacher-led-instruction, increased students interaction and engagement, group work and projects and quality learning time, amongst others. The study discovered that deployment of instructional materials varies based on location, as the urban are more favorably placed to have modern and up-to-date instructional material for the smooth teaching and learning of the subject while the reverse is the case with the rural areas under investigation. Conclusively, the study discovered that teachers are still favourable to the use of out-dated instructional material as against the modern one that has the capacity to enhance and improve learning outcome amongst students; and also, where instructional materials are available, the teacher with the relevant expertise to deploy it for academic purposes are not available, especially at the rural area giving impetus to the uneven distribution of social studies teachers on the basis of urban and rural dichotomy.

Keywords: Instructional Material, Location, Social Studies.

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Introduction

Social Studies education is one of the academic programmes being hosted at the Upper Basic secondary school in Nigeria. It was formally experimented at Ayetoro Comprehensive College at its introduction in the early 60s. It means that this course of study has been with us for well over 50 years. After this over five decades of the discipline, doubt still exists as per the influence of deployed instructional material constitute in the effective and efficient delivery of some lessons by many teachers of Social Studies. The effects of globalization on every spheres of life in society has its impact on education, thereby imposing the challenge on teachers in the deployment of the available but appropriate and relevant instructional materials for pedagogical implementation of lesson in social studies at the secondary school levels.

Deployment of instructional materials conceptually relates to the adopted and adapted materials the experience, qualified and specialized teacher in social studies education comes to class with to be used to teach a given lesson with the aim to promote learning among learners. Interest in learning a given topic in Social Studies classroom is linked with the teacher's ability to deploy the relevant instructional materials. This is because instructional materials ranked second most important resources after the teacher that drive teaching and learning. Lewis (2018) described teaching learning materials to mean the collection of any materials which could be inanimate and animate objects and human and non-human resources that a teacher may use in teaching and learning situations. The goal is to enable the class teacher to achieve desired learning objectives. Lewis also indicated that instructional materials may aid a student in concretizing a learning experience so as to make learning more exciting, interesting and interactive. The IGI Global (2019) indicated that instructional materials are deployable tools used in instructional activities, which include active learning and assessment. This knowledge of how to deploy instructional material in the execution of lesson in social studies classroom for teacher cannot be overstressed.

Teachers' supply in public schools across Nigeria is the responsibility of government; while state government is concerned with secondary school education, the recruitment, employment, engagement and distribution of teachers is assigned to state education board. Consequently, State Post Primary Board (SPPB) in case of Delta State is assigned with the spatial distribution of teachers to urban and rural locations. The factor of teacher location is consistently debated in relation to the advantage it has for teachers in urban and rural when assessing their deployment of instructional materials. Spatial distribution of teachers in many states including Delta State has been a problematic issues and a major challenge in the teaching profession. Resistant to transfer and or outright rejection of posting to environments considered unfavourable to working conditions by most teaching staff is an observable recurrent decimal in the secondary school system. Comparative studies have been ongoing to test the difficulties encountered by both teachers in urban and rural schools. Thus, the deployment of instructional materials in secondary school appears to be moderated by the variable of location.

Okobia (2011) and Egwu (2020) were concerned about the challenges facing the implementation of Social Studies in junior secondary schools in Nigeria. They observed that the challenge is linked with the grossly inadequate instructional materials meant for the teaching and learning of the subject. They believed that where the instructional materials are available, specialist and non specialist Social Studies teachers would be able to effectively and efficiently implement the contents of the curriculum. The study by Abdu-Raheem (2016) revealed that instructional materials positively contribute to students' academic achievement in terms of test scores. According to him, students who are taught with instructional materials performed better than those taught without. It means that instructional materials are very important for teachers who are responsible for curriculum implementation. It is against this backdrop the study examines the correlates between the deployment of instructional materials and teachers distribution in urban and rural location in Delta State.

Social Studies Education in the 21st Century

Education in the 21st century is a connotation which according to Rich (2010) refers to certain core competencies such as collaboration, digital literacy, critical thinking and problem-solving skills. She stated these elements of education that described the 21st century learning is believed by advocates that schools need to teach to help students thrive in today's world. The four elements that seem to represent learning in the 21st century are paradigms found in the contents of Social Studies education particularly at the secondary school system in Nigeria. Social Studies teachers employ collaborative learning as a method of teaching. The method is used to encourage students to work together on a material to be learnt in small groups to achieve the completion of school course work. There is a growing awareness among teachers and students about the rise of digital literacy in Nigeria. There is increase desire for digital literacy among Nigerian youth in response to globalization. Heitin (2016) stated that digital literacy is the ability to use information and communication technologies to find, evaluate, create and communicate information requiring both cognitive and technical skills. Learning in Social Studies has the objective of developing in learner the ability of critical thinking (Osakwe, 2010), and problem-solving skills in social, economic and political environment. The implication of the four elements of the 21st century learning components suggest that Social Studies education is the type of learning that can improve a persons' knowledge of national economy in the 21st century. The challenge of the discipline appears to be affected by the type of instructional materials deployed by the school to achieve its learning objectives that could make the subject global complaint.

Instructional Materials in Social Studies in the 21st Century

Researchers have identified new approaches in the development of instructional materials to be deployed for the effective and efficient teaching of the subject in most 21st century Social Studies classroom. Chemwei and Tuimur (2015) citing Kochhar (1991) listed some of the instructional materials necessary for effective teaching and learning of Social Studies to include the chalkboard, models, graphs, charts, maps, pictures, diagrams, cartoons, slides, film-strups, radio and television. This list is not exhaustive because they seem to be

more of traditional instructional materials whereas recent trends suggests that most classrooms are configure to use sophisticated technologies driven by the Internet with the aim of making learning to be a global experience. Thus, digitalizing the classroom has become the new trend in the theory and practice of education. Nigeria is a part of the globalized learning communities. It is ideal that learner in Social Studies should experience learning in a digitalized classroom. This type of learning deploys technology or by instructional practice that makes effective use of technology. It encompasses the application of a wide spectrum of practice including blended and virtual learning. It makes learning a global experience from the vintage of the learners' environment. Globalization has turned the world to a global village. Teachers are to take advantage of the positive impact of the increasing facilities from the global atmosphere to assist their students.

It is a global trend in the 21st century Social Studies to implement a digital curriculum. Observation indicates that a digital classroom enables teachers to blend learning in Social Studies that incorporates multiple methods of instruction. The idea of the digital classroom is technological driven not that the technology can replace the teacher. The concept revolves around a teacher led instruction with the Social Studies students as the central focus. A typical conceptual model which illustrates the theory of a digitalized instruction for social studies learning is replicated or adopted from Live Tiles (2016)

Conceptual Model of Digital Instruction

Model Explained

The components of the model consists of the variables of:

- **Teacher-led-instruction:** In any Social Studies classroom involving the deployment of technologies, it is the duty of the teacher to guide students to use technology responsibly. This is because translating from a traditional classroom to a digital classroom requires more than just integrating technology. It requires teaching strategies to implement technology in the most effective way
- **Increased students interaction and engagement:** The central focus for deployed instructional materials including technological facilities is to promote students active and psychomotor domain and cognitive learning. A concretized learning environment is most suitable for learning Social Studies concepts with digital contexts
- **Group work and projects:** technology encouraged group learning more than traditional method of instruction. This is because, technology makes it possible for connectivity and networking of ideas as well as collaboration on common projects. Computers with Internet access simplify group assignment in terms of sharing, downloading and uploading of materials within a minute of click.
- **Quality learning time:** The use of technology in the Social Studies classroom according to Meyerson (2016) enables students to have control over their own learning. She stated that students would be able to self regulate and reflect on their learning. They know how brain functions and are able to understand the process of learning which is made explicit to them. Actualizing learning involving the adoption of technology imposes a lot of challenge to teachers of Social Studies at the secondary school level.

Teaching Upper Basic Social Studies

The Upper Basic Social Studies programme of the Universal Basic Education (UBE) is 3 years of Junior Secondary Education. It is a phase of education at the secondary school level for years 7,8 and 9 which helps to ensure that the bridge between primary and secondary school is safe, strong and consistent for all students. Junior secondary school focuses on age-appropriate education and support for students' well-being and transitions. The success of the programme has been challenged by many factors. Some of which have been outlined as follows:

- **Teacher Factor:** teachers are the most valuable instructional resources in the school system. The imperative nature of teaching and learning suggests that the teacher is the first consideration for any useful learning experience. Whatever type of instructional materials available for learning it is the teacher who organizes and direct their deployment in the classroom situation. Teaching materials can support students learning and increases students' success to the extent to which teacher is able to assist their learning using the appropriate materials. According to Nwanekezi and Ibekwe (2017), teachers' academic qualification and years of teaching experience are important moderating variables because they determine the teachers quality and competence in the selection of instructional materials.

- **Teacher Knowledge in Technology:** Technological facilities have almost become the main stay of education practice globally. Delivery of instruction in most social studies classroom deploys system approach involving the computer with Internet fittings. The adaptation of the technologies such as Power-point presentation of contents, browsing skills, computer typing skills and search engines for researching into the world wide web (www) imposes enormous challenge on most social studies teachers who were not initially trained in the Information Communication Technology (ICT). Lack of knowledge in the use of the apparatus of the ICT for instruction reduces students interaction with their global; counterparts. Whereas learning via technology is the trend in the 21st century. Bolick (2016) was of the view that preparing pre-service teachers to be proficient in technology is a key issue for the field of education. According to her, new technologies are disseminated into many schools at a rapid rate. Consequently, to use these ICT facilities effectively,, teachers need not only to be proficient in technology but also well versed in the effective integration of technology into their instruction. The implication on education is that students under a teacher without knowledge in the domain of technology will be deprived the opportunities that comes with instruction using technology.
- **Teacher Location:** The spatial distribution of teachers takes them to either the urban or rural school locations. From observation, it could be perceived that a greater population of teachers of social studies are founds in urban schools, leaving a scanty ratio of teachers at the rural schools. The effect of the uneven distribution of social studies teachers is that learning gap would be created between urban and rural schools in terms of the following:
 - Available and utilized instructional materials
 - Learning outcome differentiations
 - Class attendance
 - School discipline
 - Completing scheme of work

The effect of the above listed variables rank higher and bears impact on academic achievement in the rural schools. This is because most teachers prefer to live in urban city considered to contain more of opportunities for quality life since there is abundant of government presence such as good road, electricity, portable water supply, means of transportation, access to school, health care services, means of communication such as Internet connectivity, amongst others including business opportunity due to the fact of density population in the cities. These are seemingly lacking at the rural areas. Also, the urban cities present learning environment for teachers and students alike because of the availability of centres such as public libraries, cyber café, and other educational institutions that encourage upgrade for teachers and self-regulated learning for students. It means that the rural area imposes serious challenge both for teachers and students in the teaching and learning of social studies.

- **Teacher Specialization:** Subject matter specialization is one of the issues for consideration in the 21st century education. Social Studies is a specialized subject area

in the school system. The concept is the act of being restricted to some specific, the instance being a Social Studies subject specialization. Teacher education programmes allow aspiring educators to choose what subject area and level they intend to teach. Students must then go on to earn licensure upon completion of a programme from teacher registration council to become a professional teacher in the individual respective subject-area. Teacher subject or course specialization refers to the training the teacher received in their subject specialization where they were also taught the methodology of teaching. This means that social studies teachers are trained in social studies methodology. They are exclusively responsible for the implementation of contents of its curriculum. Their pedagogical content knowledge makes it easy for students to learn and understand non specialist social studies teachers. The difference between a specialist social studies teachers and the non specialist teacher is the traits they come to class with. There is a high level of self-concept, self-motivation and enthusiasm demonstrated by teachers whose course of study was social studies major. These categories of teachers have the key and skill to create interesting classroom interactions. This experience will be lacking from a non specialist social studies teachers drafted from related subject-matter. Most teachers in this category struggle to implement contents of the curriculum. This is because there were not previous.

Challenges Facing Deployment of Instructional Materials

The relative impact of traditional instructional materials such as textbooks, charts, chalkboard, cartoon where they are available and deployed by teachers have not been able to promote global learning. The 21st century learning in social studies involves instructional materials that will encourage learning that could enhance collaboration (Egwu, 2022). Adaptation of digitalized facilities for instruction has become the trend in education practice globally. The fact that most social studies teachers in Delta State and Nigeria in general were not trained in the skills involving the application of the infrastructure of ICT, teaching and learning in most classroom in many schools in the state hardly deploys technology as a medium of instruction; whereas, exposure to a classroom with technology is the ideal form of learning because it boasts learners' critical thinking and problem solving skills. Learning that is visualized increases learning perception. Thus, learning outcome in terms of achievement in test scores will greatly improve against learning that is abstract in nature. Consequently, it remains a challenge for students whose classroom deploys only traditional means of instruction.

Conclusion and Suggestion

The study concludes that teaching without deployment of technology for social studies learning will consistently affect students' suitability in modern society driven by technology. Learning via technology affords learners to access the world from their classroom. This is the trend of education in the 21st century. It is against this backdrop, social studies teachers in urban and rural schools should make efforts to acquire ICT skill so that they can instruct using the apparatus of technology. State government should install

technology facilities in secondary schools to make it easy for both teachers and students to take advantage of global learning that has become the main stay of education delivery around the world.

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